

***Akimerus schaefferi dentipes* (Mulsant, 1842) rest. nom. from
France and *Etorofus pubescens minetti* ssp. nov. from France
(Coleoptera: Cerambycidae)**

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Abstract. *Akimerus schaefferi dentipes* (Mulsant, 1842) **rest. nom.** was compared with *A. s. schaefferi* (Laicharting, 1784), *A. s. ariannae* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007, *A. berchmansii* Breit, 1915, and *Etorofus pubescens minetti* **ssp. nov.** was compared with *E. p. pubescens* (Fabricius, 1787).

Materials and methods

Acronyms of collections:

JV - collection of J. Vartanis (Uherský Brod, Czech Republic);

ML - collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia);

MS - collection of M. Sláma (Praha, Czechia);

RM - collection of R. Minetti (France).

Results

***Akimerus schaefferi dentipes* (Mulsant, 1842) rest. nom.**

Plate 1

Body stocky, antennae thick, slightly shorter than the body. Third to fifth antennomeres strongly knotted and widened at the end. Pronotum with two large bumps on the surface, coarsely wrinkled and dotted, with a longitudinal groove in the middle. Elytra in females, only about 2.5 times longer than wide at the base, very strongly narrowed posteriorly, more finely wrinkled at the base. Females reddish-yellow, abdominal sternite densely golden-yellow hairy.

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Elytra in females very sparsely hairy, seemingly bare, without a visible yellow transverse band at its apex in the middle (see photograph), a very different character from the typical species *A. s. schaefferi* (Laicharting, 1784). In males, the elytra are very narrow, up to 3.5 times longer than wide at the base, orange-yellow (see photo), these two visible features are very different from the typical species *A. s. schaefferi* (Laicharting, 1784). The species is currently found only in France.

Body size: males 18-22 mm, females 23-26 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new subspecies *A. s. dentipes* (Mulsant, 1842) **rest. nom.** occurs so far in France, where from book sources from French colleagues, this species occurs very rarely, mainly on trees (*Quercus*), and is captured individually and rarely in various localities. Very characteristic features for this new subspecies are mainly in females, where the transverse yellow band in the middle of the elytron is missing, as can be seen in the photo below. Males show the color of the elytron more orange-yellow, are slimmer and at the base are 3.55x wider than the length of the elytron. It was compared with the species *A. s. schaefferi* (Laicharting, 1784), which occurs mainly in Central Europe (Czech Republic, Slovakia, Austria, Germany, Ukraine, Hungary and some destinations in the Balkans), the species occurs very rarely in native forests (*Quercus*). Females are reddish-brown, with a transverse yellow band in the middle of the elytron. Males are more stocky, the width of the shoulders at the base is only 3 times longer than the length of the elytron. In Greece, another endemic species occurs, *A. s. ariannae* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007, where females are reddish-brown to completely black with a characteristic yellow transverse band in the middle of the elytron. In males, the width of the shoulders at the base is only 3 times longer than the length of the elytron. The last species *A. berchmansii* Breit, 1915, is found only in Turkey, at first glance a very different species, where the females are mostly all black, and show a very distinct, bordered, yellow longitudinal band in the middle of the elytron. The males are half all black, or dark red with a black vertical band on the elytron.

Plate - 1

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A new subspecies from France, *A. s. dentipes* (Mulsant, 1842) **rest. nom.** shows very distinctive features for a new subspecies, which in biological systematics is a subspecies taxon denoting individual with their own morphological characters that differ from another subspecies of the same species.

Material. 1 female, France, Deblois, 20.VII.1996, Auvray lgt. - JV; 3 females, France, Deblois, VII.1998, lgt. Auvray - MS; 1 male, 1 female, France, de Blois, 19.VII.1994, N. Auvray leg. - ML; 1 female, France - 41000, Blois St. Sulpice env, 100 m, 47.60°N 01.26°E, 15.7.1996, C. Auvray leg. - ML; 1 male, France, Aiguines Forêt de Margés, 3.VIII.1979, P.Berger lgt. - MS; 1 male, France, Aiguines, 7.VII. 2018, J.Steinhofer lgt. - MS; 1 male, 1 female, France, Ft. De Morieives, VI.2004, Pascala Stefani lgt. - MS; 1 male, 2 females France - MS; 5 males, France, Forêt Domaniale de Russy, VII. 1998, Minetti lgt. - JV; 2 males, 3 females, France, Molineuf, 6.VII.1992, Machard lgt.; 4 males, France, Ft. De Boulogne, 12.VII.1996 - RM.

Species distribution.

1. *Akimerus schaefferi schaefferi* (Laicharting, 1784): Austria, Czechia, Slovakia, Ukraina, Hungary, Croatia, Germany, Polonia, Romania.
2. *Akimerus schaefferi ariannae* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007: Greece.
3. *Akimerus berchmansii* Breit, 1915: Turkey.
4. *Akimerus schaefferi dentipes* (Mulsant, 1842) **rest. nom.** France.

Bionomics. The occurrence of the subspecies is always dependent on the presence of very old *Quercus*, or *Quercet* of stump origin. In warm weather, the adults fly around the crowns and in the crowns of trees, perching on the leaves of the trees.

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***Etorofus pubescens minetti* ssp. nov.**

Plate 2

Pronotum black, very densely granular with long, dense golden pubescence, which is very long. Antennae dark brown to black, 3rd antennomeres in both males and females, shorter than 4th and 5th antennomeres together. 4th and 5th antennomeres are 1.76x together longer than 3rd antennomeres. Elytra yellow, very densely granular, gaps smaller than dots themselves, very long adjacent pubescence. Length of elytron is 2.9x longer than at base wide. This is a very narrow, long species, compared to the nominal form. Abdominal sternite, very sparsely pubescent, almost glabrous. Pieces from France show very different characters, for a new subspecies *Etorofus pubescens minetti* ssp. nov.

Body size: males 13-15 mm, females 15-17 mm.

Material. Holotype, male, France, Val d'Escrin, Vars (04), 29.VI.2001, R. Minetti lgt. - JV; 60 Paratypes: 8 males, 6 females, France, Val d'Escrin, Vars (04), 29.VI.2001, R. Minetti lgt. - JV, RM; 5 males, 5 females, France, Col du Labouret, 4.VII. 2015 , R. Minetti lgt. - JV, RM; 5 males, 4 females, France, Col du Labouret, 27.VI.2001, R.Minetti lgt. - JV, RM; 7 males, 3 females, France, Chateau Queyras, VII.1999 - JV, RM; 3 males, 2 females, VII.2004 - JV, RM; 2 males, 7.VII.1961- JV, RM; 4 males, 1 female, France, Coulloubroux, VII.1987 - JV, RM; 3 males, 2 females, France, Col de Vars, 4.VII.2014 - 1.VII.2018, R.Minetti lgt. - JV, RM.

Differential diagnosis: The specimens of the new species, so far endemic to France, *E. p. minetti* ssp. nov., show very different characters, characteristic of the new subspecies. I have listed the different characters in the description and also documented them in the photograph on plate number 2. There are many specimens in the collections. *E. p. pubescens* (Fabricius, 1787) (Czechia, Slovakia, Austria, Balkán, Greece), pronotum black, very sparsely granular with short golden pubescence, which is shorter than in the new species *E. p. minetti* ssp. nov. Antennae dark brown, 3rd antennomeres in both males and females, very long, almost as long as 4th and 5th antennomeres together. 4th and 5th antennomeres are only 1.33 times longer together than 3rd antennomeres.

Plate - 2

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Elytra yellow, very finely, gaps larger than dots themselves, very short and sparsely adjacent pubescence. Length of elytron 2.6 times longer than at base wide. This is a less narrow species, compared to the new species. Abdominal sternite, very densely, long adjacent pubescence. Pieces of the species *E. p. pubescens*, from different areas and destinations in Europe show very different characters, compared to the new subspecies *E. p. minetti* **ssp. nov.**

Bionomics. Development in coniferous trees, imago on flowers, 6th-7th month.

Etymology. The new subspecies *Etorofus pubescens minetti* **ssp. nov.**, received its name from the French colleague R. Minetti, who discovered this species in several locations in France.

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